

MODERN INDUSTRIAL PROCESSES FOR PROCESSING “ACID” GAS, BASED ON THE DIRECT OXIDATION REACTION OF HYDROGEN SULFIDE

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Catasulf process from the German company BASF is based on the oxidation reaction of “acid” gas containing 5–15% H_2S (I) in a tubular reactor 1 (Fig. 1). The tube space of reactor 1 is filled with a special highly selective catalyst, which is a mixture of aluminum, nickel and vanadium oxides, and the inter-tube space is cooled by a high-boiling liquid organosilicon coolant (II), which, when circulating, gives off the removed heat in refrigerator 2.

Rice. 1. Catasulf process diagram

The gases leaving the reactor 1, (III) are cooled in the sulfur condenser 3 and fed into the adiabatic reactor 4, where further interaction of hydrogen sulfide with sulfur dioxide occurs. The resulting sulfur is separated in the second sequential condenser 5. Sulfur recovery at the first stage is 94%, after the adiabatic reactor - up to 97.5%. It is claimed that by increasing the number of stages, sulfur recovery rates of up to 99.99% can be achieved. The oil refinery in Ludwigshafen (Germany) operates the only industrial Catasulf unit to date [1].

Catasulf process is perhaps the only "operational" large-scale technology for producing sulfur from hydrogen sulfide based on the direct oxidation reaction of hydrogen sulfide. Other industrial processes based on this reaction have been developed exclusively for the purification of off-gases from existing sulfur recovery plants [2].

One of the most common methods is BSR/ Selectox from Unocal and Ralph. M. _ Parsons . In this process, the waste gases of the Claus plant are reduced in a catalytic reactor with synthesis gas, which is formed in a special generator during the steam reforming of natural gas. Then the resulting gas is cooled, after which it is mixed with air, and H₂S undergoes selective oxidation to sulfur at a temperature of 200–230 °C. The use of a special vanadium oxide catalyst Selestox-67 allows achieving selectivity of oxidation to sulfur of about 100%. Beavon-Selectox process ensures achievement of a sulfur recovery rate of 98.5–99.5% at a relatively low installation cost (about 50–60% of the cost of a Claus installation [27]). The first such installation was launched in 1978 in Germany.

Somewhat later , other technologies similar to the Beavon-Selectox process were developed . Among them, the most famous are MODOP from Mobil. Oil Corp. _ They differ from the Beavon-Selectox process in the use of other catalysts (CRS-31 for MODOP and a special highly selective iron oxide catalyst for the SUPERCLAUS process), and also in the fact that the oxidation of hydrogen sulfide can be carried out in two stages. In addition , the SUPERCLAUS process provides for the possibility of using a direct oxidation stage of H₂S without a hydrogenation stage, due to the fact that in the Claus installation itself the process is carried out with an excess of hydrogen sulfide (this allows, among other things, to protect the catalyst in Claus reactors from sulfation). These processes provide a total sulfur recovery of 99.3–99.5%. The first two MODOP installations were put into operation in Germany in 1983 and 1987, and two SUPERCLAUS installations - in 1988 in Germany and in 1989 in Holland.

The advantage of the described processes is the ability to supply air for the oxidation of hydrogen sulfide in a slight excess compared to stoichiometry, which simplifies process control under conditions of fluctuations in the composition and flow rate of the reaction mixture.

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